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PHYTOCHEMICAL EXTRACTION OF STEM OF *SIDA ACUTA* BURM. F.

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ABSTRACT

Plants and plant based products are bases of many modern pharmaceuticals that are currently in use today for various diseases. *Sida acuta* Burm. f. belonging to Malvaceae is a perennial shrub found growing, well in many soils. The plant is frequently found in pastures, cultivated lands and along the roadsides. It has a variety of traditional uses. The decoction of the entire plant is taken orally for curing asthma, fever, aches and pains, ulcers and also several other diseases. *Sida acuta* is known to have analgesic, anti-inflammatory, hypoglycemic and hepatoprotective activity. The present study was undertaken to analyse the various phytochemical constituents in the stem of *Sida acuta*. The phytochemical investigation revealed the presence of various phytoconstituents such as Alkaloids, Phenols, tannis, Proteins and amino acids. However, it also contains small amount of Carbohydrates and glycosides.

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INTRODUCTION

Plants are the producers of every primary and secondary metabolites of high structural diversity. Secondary metabolites include alkaloids, phenols, terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, and many other essential oils etc. These secondary metabolites has a variety of traditional uses¹. The knowledge of their medicinal properties has been transformed from one generation to the next generation of the human communities over the centuries. According to world health organization (who), medicinal plants may be the best source of variety of potential drugs and about 80% population of the world depend on traditional herbal medicine for their primary health care².

Sida acuta Burm.f. belongs to Malvaceae is a perennial shrub found growing, grow well in many soils. The plant is frequently found in pastures, cultivated lands and along the roadsides. It has a variety of traditional uses. In Nicaragua the decoction of the entire plant is taken orally for curing asthma, fever, aches and pains, ulcers and also venereal disease^{3,4}.

In India, the hot water extract of the dried entire plant is administered orally as a febrifuge, an abortifacient and diuretic⁵. Previously, antibacterial and antifungal activities of crude extracts of *Sida acuta* have been reported⁶⁻⁸. The aim of the present investigation is to extract and screen flavonoids (free and bound) from different parts (root, stem, leaf and buds) of *Sida acuta* for their antimicrobial activity.

All the plant parts of *Sida acuta* exert various pharmacological properties includes antiplasmodial, antimicrobial, antioxidant and cytotoxic activities. In Kenya, the whole plant is used to prepare 'Bundugo', a supplementary strength magically added to a person⁹. In western Colombia, whole plant is used for snake bites¹⁰ and in India, it is used for fever, bronchitis, ulcer, diarrhea, dysentery and skin diseases.¹¹ The leaves are used for the treatment of eczema, kidney stone, headache, malaria, gonorrhoea, breast cancer, poisoning inflammation, stops bleeding, sores and wounds¹²⁻¹⁴. The paste of leaves is mixed with coconut oil and applied on head regularly for killing dandruffs and also for strengthening hair¹⁵.

The aim of the present investigation is to extract and screen various secondary metabolites such as flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, tannins, terpenoids etc from the leaves of *Sida acuta*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

Plants material was collected from vindhya herbals, Bhopal during the month of September 2016.

Plant identification:

The collected plant material was identified based on the literature available.

Processing of plant materials

The stem bark was washed in running tap water and cut into small bits to facilitate drying. The plant material was then dried under shade at room temperature. The dried plant material (stem bark) was taken and ground using an electric blender to obtain a fine powder. The powdered sample was used for further analysis.

Solvent extraction

About 20g portions of powdered plant material was dispersed in 200 ml of each 70% methanol, chloroform and petroleum ether. The solution was left to stand at room temperature for 3-4 days and was then filtered with Whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrate was used for the phytochemical screening using the following tests.

Phytochemical extraction of drug

Phytochemical examinations were carried out for all the extracts as per the following standard methods.

1. Plant Constituents----- Alkaloids

Test/Reagent Used----- Mayer's Reagent

Preparation of Reagent---(a) 1.36g of mercuric chloride in 60 ml of D.W.

(b) 5g of potassium iodide in 20 ml of D. W.

Adjust the vol. of 100 ml with D.W.

Reaction---- 1 ml filtrate was taken and few drops of Mayer's reagent was added & the formation of cream color precipitate was observed. This confirms the presence of Alkaloids in the plant Extract.

2. Plant Constituents-----Carbohydrates & glycosides

Test/Reagent Used-----Fehling Solution

Preparation of Reagent--It is used for detection of reducing sugars. Dissolve 34.66g of copper sulphate in D.W. & make the volume up to 500ml (sol. A). Dissolve 173g of potassium sodium tartarate and 50g of sodium hydroxide in D.W. & make volume up to 500 ml (sol.B). Mix equal volume prior to use.

Reaction--- 1 ml filtrate was taken and few drops of Fehling solution was added & the formation of a red precipitate was observed. This confirms the presence of Carbohydrates & glycosides in the plant extract.

3. Plant Constituents-----Phenolic compounds & tannins**Test/Reagent Used**-----Ferric Chloride solution**Preparation of Reagent**---A 5% W/V solution of ferric chloride in 90% alcohol and used for detection of phenols.**Reaction**---1ml filtrate was taken and few drops of Ferric chloride solution was added & The formation of a bluish black coloration was observed. This confirms the presence of Phenolic compounds & tannins.**4. Plant Constituents**-----Proteins & Amino acids**Test/Reagent Used**-----Ninhydrin test**Preparation of Reagent**--Prepare 0.1% solution in n-butanol.**Reaction**--- 1ml filtrates was taken and few drops of Ninhydrin was added & the Formation of a purplish pink coloration was observed. This confirms the presence of Proteins & Amino acids.**RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

Phytochemical estimation of the plant showed the presence of various bioactive compounds for all the three solvents used. Qualitative analysis of revealed the presence of more number of phytochemical in the methanolic extract of *Sida acuta* compared with other two solvents. The results of these phytochemicals are listed in the table 1 given below.

Table1 Depicting phytochemical analysis of drug extract.

Phytochemical tests	<i>Sida acuta</i>		
	Chloroform	Methanol	Petroleum ether
Alkaloids (Mayers Reagent)	-	+	-
Carbohydrates & glycosides (Fehling Solution)	-	+	-
Phenolic compounds & tannins (Ferric Chloride solution)	+	-	+
Proteins/Aminoacids (Ninhydrin test)	-	+	+

CONCLUSION

Sida acuta has been utilized from long time. All parts of the plant, including leaves, bark, root, seeds and flower possess great significance in phytomedicine. Phytochemical investigation of the plant stem shows the presence different bioactive constituents such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, tannins, phenolic compounds, glycosides, proteins etc for all the three solvents used which significantly account for its multiple properties and uses. Hence *Sida acuta* will serve as an important phytomedicine in pharmacology for the eradication of various diseases.

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